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THEORETICAL STUDY OF THE PROCESS OF PROCESSING AND RECYCLING HOUSEHOLD WASTE

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ABSTRACT

This article covers the implementation of measures to reduce the amount of waste that is transported (transported) to large landfills, recycled, stored, and sent to special production facilities and storage areas during the processing of solid household waste. The crushing and processing of solid household waste creates the opportunity to separate useful components for further use, and the effectiveness of the work is discussed.

Keywords: criterion, solid household waste, recycling, organic waste, hammer.

INTRODUCTION

The most objective criteria for the validity and usefulness of all new products are human experience. However, it is not always possible to carry out a long-term and technical test of each new technical solution. For this reason, in various fields of science and technology, including in the field of mineral raw materials processing, in order to optimize the management of production process data, to compare and select appropriate technological schemes, one or another criterion is proposed for optimizing the developed parameters of machines or a specific technological process.

The integral criteria of mechanical systems include: productivity, efficiency, energy and raw material consumption, relative power, metal consumption, useful work coefficient, reliability in operation, average value of kinematic and dynamic characteristics, etc.

They are called by different names: energy consumption, efficiency and power mode, raw material and energy consumption [1,2], power, long-term durability, stability, reliability [3], KPD, etc. With the development of multi-criteria optimization of mechanical systems, generalized criteria have emerged, obtained by converting several complex criteria into one, which are the components of the complex criteria and are identical to the proposed system.

The Sobolya-Statnikov method [4] is widely used in the search for optimal parameters of mechanical systems and is based on the following:

1. Design tasks are multi-criteria. There are many criteria, the improvement of which is of interest to the customer.

2. It is impossible to describe a solution of the proposed options that would fully and sufficiently take into account all the goals of processing and the creation of a mechanical system, reducing the problem to a single criterion.

In fact, the Sobolya-Statnikov method is a method for formulating and solving the problem of determining the sets of permissible solutions, their informal analysis, and determining the optimal operation of the created mechanical system. This allows taking into account many criteria that the developer considers necessary for full optimization of the system.

The most common integral criterion for evaluating processing equipment is the processing efficiency criterion (per shift, per month, per year). However, in general, these criteria do not take into account either energy consumption, or the metal intensity of the equipment used in the process, or costs, and many other indicators. Naturally, these indicators are not suitable for comparing different processing systems.

However, the performance criterion and the total energy consumption criterion are the only criteria that are suitable.

The technological process should be optimized with a clearly defined set of equipment. In such cases, this is done by optimizing the parameters of this equipment.

The cost of 1 m³ of the resulting product is currently accepted as the main criterion for assessing the efficiency of various methods of processing technological machines. The cost value is calculated taking into account the costs necessary to ensure the processing process, i.e. labor, electricity, materials, depreciation costs, transport repair services, etc. These criteria are currently the most widely used and are considered objective. However, it should be noted that this criterion is more influenced by subjective and market factors than others, since it is formed by indicators such as price, wages, depreciation and services. These indicators depend on market conditions, available raw materials and labor resources, the geographical and economic zoning of the country, and the need for secondary raw materials.

METHOD

The desire of researchers to combine several criteria into one universal criterion led to the creation of the direction of multi-criteria optimization. There are two ways to solve such problems.

The first way is the rating method, which is a method in which a composite criterion is determined from the selected K_1, K_2, \dots, K_n performance criteria, and it is as follows.

$$\sum_{j=1}^n K = a_1 K_1 + a_2 K_2 + \dots + a_n K_n$$

An attempt was made to develop a generalized criterion, or in other words, generalized efficiency indicators, for assessing the efficiency of road and construction machines, in particular, crushers, during operation.

The essence of the method is as follows: at the stage of developing a new technology, it is recommended to establish the efficiency of the latter using approximate dependencies, the basis for the formation of which is a systematic analysis of the object being evaluated. A systematic classification of an object corresponding to the level of the main groups of machine subsystems allows us to consider the reduced costs in the form of the sum of each of the terms characterizing a particular group of machine subsystems:

1) the costs of creating a power subsystem, the value of which is proportional to the power of the installed electric motor according to the first approximation;

2) the cost of creating a technological or functional subsystem of the machine, determined by its design (working parts, frame, automation, etc.), is proportional to the mass (weight force) of the machine;

The value Z can be expressed as the sum of the following:

$$Z = b_0^1 + b_1 N + b_2 G$$

Analysis of these directions of multi-criteria optimization shows that the accuracy of the rating method depends on the completeness of the accounting and the degree of influence of each factor on the efficiency of the mechanical system. In operating conditions, the importance of each factor is assessed independently, and their selection is largely random. In addition, the rating method is based on assessing the efficiency of the equipment by relative indicators, combining them into a complex indicator, using weighting coefficients determined by subjective and labor-intensive specialists.

The second method is also not devoid of subjectivity, since the imposed restrictions are essentially set in an unreasonable manner.

An analysis of the above two methods for determining the efficiency criterion of the designed machine for the case of creating a crusher for crushing solid household waste shows that none of the above methods fully meets the required technical, economic, social and environmental requirements.

CONCLUSION

1. To develop criteria for assessing the efficiency of hammer crushers used in the crushing of household waste, an integrated approach is required, fully covering technical, economic, social and economic quality criteria.

2. It is recommended to use technical and economic indicators (energy density, material density, etc.) based on the specifics of the problem being solved. The efficiency criterion of the designed machine is optimized according to the first integral method of determining, since the assessment of efficiency and technical level based on a given unit cost requires a preliminary determination of the values of the coefficients, and this complicates the process of assessing b_0^1, b_1, b_2 .

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